

18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri
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18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybider Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 13 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Krallık, Cezayir, Çin, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 72'i Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 80'i farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 152 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta bilim insanlarının kongrede sunduğu bildirilerin tam metinlerine yer verilmiştir. Bu sunumların geniş kitlelere ulaşarak alana faydalı olmasını ve yeni çalışmalara ilham vermesini diliyorum.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Yakup Civelek
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يأتي هذا الكتاب نتيجًا لجهود مجموعة من الباحثين البارزين الذين شاركوا بأبحاثهم في المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، والذي عُقد في أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. يعد هذا المؤتمر أحد أبرز الفعاليات الأكاديمية التي تجمع بين مختلف التخصصات في مجال العلوم الإنسانية، حيث شارك فيه باحثون من أكثر من عشرين دولة من مختلف القارات، مما أضفى طابعًا عالميًا ومتنوعًا على المناقشات التي جرت.

تميز المؤتمر بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي الذي انعكس في الأوراق البحثية المقدمة، حيث تناول الباحثون قضايا متعددة تشمل الأدب الكلاسيكي والمعاصر، اللغات الحديثة والقديمة، ودراسات الثقافة وتأثيراتها على المجتمعات المختلفة. ولم يقتصر النقاش على دراسة الأعمال الأدبية أو تحليل النصوص اللغوية فحسب، بل تطرق إلى استكشاف العلاقة بين اللغة والثقافة وكيف تساهم في تشكيل الهويات الفردية والجماعية.

تمحورت العديد من الأبحاث حول قضايا مثل تأثير العولمة على اللغات والثقافات المحلية، وكيفية المحافظة على التراث الثقافي واللغوي في مواجهة التغيرات المتسارعة. كما سلطت الأبحاث الضوء على دور الأدب في نقل التجارب الإنسانية والتعبير عن القضايا الاجتماعية والسياسية، ما أضاف أبعادًا جديدة لفهمنا للأدب كوسيلة للتغيير الاجتماعي والثقافي. في هذا السياق، عُرضت دراسات معمقة حول الترجمة ودورها في بناء جسور بين الثقافات المختلفة، حيث كانت الترجمة موضوعًا محوريًا في العديد من الأبحاث التي ناقشت التحديات التي تواجه المترجمين في نقل النصوص بما يحافظ على أصالتها وسياقها الثقافي. وقد أضافت هذه الأبحاث أبعادًا جديدة للفهم العالمي للأدب واللغة كوسائل لتبادل الأفكار والتجارب بين الشعوب.

من الجدير بالذكر أن المؤتمر تناول أيضًا التحولات التي تشهدها اللغات والأدب في العصر الرقمي، حيث تم تسليط الضوء على تأثير التكنولوجيا الحديثة على كيفية إنتاج النصوص الأدبية وتلقيها. وقدمت أبحاث حول كيفية توظيف الأدوات الرقمية في تحليل النصوص الأدبية، مما أتاح فرصًا جديدة للتفاعل مع الأدب بطرق مبتكرة ومختلفة.

هذا الكتاب يضم بين صفحاته نتائج عمل أكاديمي متميز يُظهر مدى التنوع والغنى الفكري الذي تمتعت به فعاليات هذا المؤتمر. فالأوراق البحثية المنشورة هنا ليست مجرد عرض لقضايا أدبية أو لغوية، بل هي محاولات جادة لاستكشاف العلاقات العميقة بين النصوص، الثقافات، والمجتمعات، وكيف يمكن أن يساهم فهم هذه العلاقات في تعزيز التواصل بين الشعوب في زمن يشهد فيه العالم تحديات متزايدة تتعلق بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي.

نأمل أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة غنية للنقاشات العلمية حول اللغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، وأن يكون محفزًا لمزيد من البحوث التي تسعى لفهم أعمق لتلك التخصصات الإنسانية التي تعد جزءًا أساسيًا من تشكيل هوياتنا وفهمنا للعالم. وختامًا، نود أن نعبر عن شكرنا لكل الباحثين الذين أسهموا بأبحاثهم في هذا المؤتمر، وكذلك لجميع الجهات المنظمة والداعمة التي ساهمت في إنجاح هذا الحدث الأكاديمي المتميز.

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The Sense of Englishness, Racial Hatred, and Xenophobia in Maggie Gee's *The White Family*

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Abstract

Unequal circumstances and unfair living conditions make people leave their hometowns and move to developed ones hoping to have a better future and reach higher living standards. However, those who flee to other countries are not welcomed and even maltreated in some parts of the world. Especially in racist countries, immigrants suffer from different sorts of violence and even lose their lives out of racial hatred. In *The White Family*, Maggie Gee depicts the misery that foreign people face in England. Those who carry pure English blood disdain non-natives, especially black people, and they cannot endure their existence in their country, which leads some of the dark racist ones to insult or harass the immigrants. The author, inspired by a real-life event, conveys a family that despises the immigrants and the family's hardships due to their racist manners, which results in a separation of the members. This paper aims to analyse the novel in regard of a sense of Englishness, racial hatred, and xenophobia by referring to some of the postcolonial scholars' premises upon the difficulties experienced not only by the immigrants but also by the natives because of racist attitudes. In this regard, the novel will be analysed in terms of racism experienced by some of the characters.

Key Words: Maggie Gee, *The White Family*, xenophobia, hatred, Englishness

Introduction

The fear of 'the other' is a global phenomenon, and it has been increasing day by day. Due to the unequal opportunities or facilities available in other countries, people are forced to flee to other countries. The term 'the other' can be defined as "an alien subjectivity, a being who exhibits characteristics notably different from our own, whether gender, race, class, custom or behaviour" (Spencer, 8), and that unease, inevitably, leads xenophobia which literary means fear of strangers, and it stems from an intense discomfort with people from divergent cultures or origins. Nowadays, xenophobia is widely used to refer to immigrants and groups of people who are seen as culturally different or inferior, especially in western countries; hence, they are seen as a kind of menace, and they are despised.

Because of economic, political, or social problems, people are obliged to leave their hometowns with the hope of better living standards and facilities. In multicultural countries, xenophobia

causes a rejection of the lifestyles, and cultural or religious values of immigrants along with limiting their basic rights for living because it is regarded as a sort of invasion of their countries. It also generates prejudices, and innocent people become a target of violent attacks, too.

In close relation to the aforementioned issues, the premise of Englishness or English nationalism refers to the privileges of native people in Britain. Those who have that sense, victimize or despise people that come from different ethnicities. Moira Ferguson clarifies the term Englishness as;

The benevolence mixed with pity and Eurocentric condescension that characterised the movement for emancipation gave way to 'biological racism', a set of ideas based on British imperial advances, a renewed sense of ethnic superiority. Englishness, what distinguished English from other cultures, was also equated with 'whiteness'. (Ferguson, 1994)

According to Ferguson, the sense of Englishness is based on a feeling of superiority in both genetics and of the country itself. In this regard, this paper scrutinizes xenophobia along with the racist attitudes of some of the characters in Maggie Gee's novel *The White Family*, which contains fear and hatred towards non-white people and the horrific outcomes of racists' irrational manners.

Published in 2002, *The White Family* centres on a theme of xenophobia as it deals with the matters of migration and also the attitudes of Englishmen towards immigrants. The sense of Englishness is very explicit within the actions and thoughts of the main characters, and their motives lead to serious troubles not only in the family but also in society. The presence of foreigners in England is regarded as an invasion that brings out a sense of fear which then turns into hatred and violence.

The novel revolves mostly around the members of the White Family. The father, named Alfred, works as a parkkeeper, and he is renowned for his hostility toward immigrants. His wife, May is a housewife, and she is depicted as more tolerant than her husband. Their daughter, Shirley is a wealthy widow but she is despised and exposed to violence by Alfred and Dirk for having relationships with black people. Further, Darren, the elder son, works as a journalist in the United States and has left home due to his father's impolite and racist manners, and Dirk is the only child who stays with the family.

The other characters are Kojo, Elroy, and Winston. Kojo is the first husband of Shirley and dies of cancer. He leaves a legacy to his wife and thanks to it, Shirley becomes independent. Elroy is the current boyfriend of Shirley who was born and grew up in London yet, he is still discriminated and regarded as a foreigner. Winston, Elroy's brother, suffers both from ethnicity and homosexuality. Each chapter of the novel is narrated by one of the members of the family and by Thomas, a librarian and an old friend of the family.

After a heart attack of the father, the family members reunite at the hospital at Alfred's side. During their visits, the author reveals some of the conflicts among the family members. Shirley, for instance, rebels against his father's racist manners, and she hits him at his nose. Due to her anger and to relieve her stress, she attends a party and meets a guy named Ivo with whom she gets pregnant at a very early age. However, after giving birth, she becomes obliged to adopt her daughter out. Dirk, the youngest son, mimics his father's racist attitudes. He is

conveyed as such a brutal boy that readers learn about his weird and sadistic personality within the scene where he tortures mice when he is a child. Darren has to leave home after a fight with his father, too. The family is depicted in very miserable conditions, and the author makes it clear that they all stem from racist attitudes of Alfred and Dirk. The author's depiction of a separated family member out of racism is significant as it implies the outcomes of hatred and fear of non-whites. The struggles of Alfred as a protector result in the separation of his own family members.

The novel begins with a quarrel of Alfred with a black family because their children have stepped on the grass. The park has a very significant value for Alfred as he states "it really has been my life" (Gee, 240). The author's displaying Alfred as the guard of the park can be interpreted as a representation of Englishness in a sense that Alfred struggles to keep the minorities away from it. He is such an obsessed racist that he cannot even stand the colourful birds that come from Africa. The novel's opening scene unrolls the disapproval of immigrants and the reactions that they are exposed to from English people. It can be stated that the author conveys the park as a miniature of England, and the keeper as the reflection of racism.

However, upon black family's objection that "the park belongs to everyone", Alfred collapses, which is also a significant scene that symbolizes the intolerance for "his failure to accept the change in British society". (Kılıç, 142). One of the main settings in the novel is Hillesden Park, a place that is open and free for everyone, and the sense of Englishness is highlighted with such a setting that it is kept by a strict Englishman who cannot endure even the black children. Maggie Gee chooses a public place with the intention of revealing the threat of intolerance towards people who are not English but invaders in the eyes of Alfred, and foreigners' presence makes him feel discontented and scared as he fails to keep them away.

Further, the author touches upon the rights of the minorities which, as Young claims, "the English did not transform themselves so easily into imagined community of a homogeneous" society (Young, 16). Foreigners' state of being wealthy is another source of fear and anger for the native people. To illustrate, Mr. Patel, a Pakiman, purchases a shop from an English man, named George, the person with whom Dirk also works. Like his father, Dirk is a racist boy and cannot tolerate foreigners, and he gets quite angry when George introduces him to the new owner of the shop. He states that "we are losing our birthright" to live in England. (Gee, 130). Moreover, he asserts that the minorities conquer England by making a claim for the properties of English people and regards minorities' right of ownership as a threat to the future of his country.

Along with immigrants' having rights to own properties, they are also able to have good positions in England. Kojo, for instance, is a very rich professor, and when he dies, Shirley inherits a considerable amount of money and can live her life freely. Shirley confesses that thanks to her husband, she is not "a poor daughter of a poor English family" anymore. However, Alfred despises him by likening Kojo to a "performing monkey" (40). Even though Kojo's kind manners to the family, he is not accepted but loathed. His superiority over Alfred and Dirk becomes a source of fear, hatred, and jealousy.

The premise of identity is also related to "who we fear or hate", and it eventually leads a boundary between the two parts (Spencer, xiv). Gee makes it clear that scare in a scene, in which Mary withdraws money from a post office. After taking the money she rushes home as

it is raining. While walking, she falls and hurts her ankle. As she collapses, all the things in her bag are scattered around. She tries to pick them up and suddenly, she notices a black man coming towards her. May describes the man as an "enormous black" with "golden eyes boring into hers" (Gee, 142). However, she has to ignore her prejudice as she becomes helpless and has nothing to do but ask for help from that black man. "Then she felt shocked and ashamed" when the man treats her very kindly. (Gee, 160). Mary's prejudgement displays the attitudes of natives towards black people. They see them as a potential menace, or they abstain from their help or support for fear of being inferior to them.

Another crucial aspect that is discussed in the novel is the impulse to preserve or the fear of losing identity. The minorities, as conveyed in the novel, do their best to adapt themselves to the country. They want to live in harmony with English people, and they speak English when they communicate with natives. For instance, Elroy uses English so fluently that he sounds "more of a Londoner" (166). Yet, Mary who is depicted as a sensitive person to her native language, criticizes the fact that the religious pamphlet about black people's church is written in American English but not in pure English.

Additionally, Dirk also despises a black bus driver for a notice that says "tender exact money". The driver claims that it is pure English but Dirk reacts disdainfully and utters that black people do not have any right to talk about English language. In this regard, the author conveys the fact that despite the efforts of non-natives, they are still regarded as lower-class people. Likewise, Elroy is an American citizen, he lives in England, and he is a fluent English speaker, yet, he is not considered as English because he does not carry pure English blood. In fact, Alfred looks down on him by stating that "he is as British as bananas" (62). He claims that Elroy does not have a right to live and work in England permanently.

Edward Said claims that the way the other is dressed leads "itself so easily to prejudices" by referring to the fact that people's wearing style is a distinctive issue that makes people contemplate on personal traits or about their ethnicity (Said, p.236, 1995). In the novel, Gee depicts the wandering minorities in London streets by stating that it is normal to see "African girls in red and orange" or "black-hooded Arab women". (363) In this sense, the minorities' clothing style is another important issue that is emphasized in the novel. The foreign people dress both in their traditional clothes and modern ones. Hence, their choices on how to dress are despised as they are not able to become pure English citizens. Alfred, who is very keen on the sense of Englishness, cannot stand to see immigrants walking in the streets with colourful clothes and protests that his country has too many foreigners.

The two parts', Englishman and immigrants', churches are also separate. It has no significance that they are all Christians. English people refuse to go to the churches in which the black people pray or carry out their religious rituals. Dunja M. Mohr claims that religious creeds have a power that "create rules about what is right or what is wrong" (91). The blacks' churches are more flexible in the sense of rules and religious ceremonies. They can dance and sing during their prayers, and they are looked down on by English people who are accustomed to deliver their prayers in silence. In this regard, the separate churches and religious services can be interpreted as intolerantness towards minorities even though they believe in the same religion.

The inevitable consequences of migration lead to social problems as well, and education is one of them. Non-natives' children face such racist treatment as the writer illustrates the miserable conditions that the black children experience. In one of the schools named *Hillesden Green Church of England School*, Gee describes a building which is "full of makeshift materials that hadn't aged well" (379). The black children outnumber the native ones yet, they do not get enough support. The government's attitude is also explicit that they do not give enough significance to the education of black children for fear of "gaining higher, better qualifications will be economically rewarding" for non-natives (Ramdin, 314). One of the students defines the classroom as a kind of prison in which nobody likes them.

The relationships of Shirley are conveyed as a sort of menace as all her affairs are with non-native people. She meets her first boyfriend Ivo, who is from the Welsh, at a party and has an affair with him that leads to a pregnancy. However, they do not meet again, and neither of them tries to keep in touch. After a couple of months, she decides to tell her secret to her father. At first, Alfred seems sympathetic but when he learns that the father of the baby is not a pure Englishman, he goes mad and states "he's a bloody darkie, isn't he?" (156). His daughter's affair with a foreigner matters more than pregnancy out of marriage for Alfred, which can be stated as an extreme example of hatred and racism.

Dirk, a dark racist, loathes black people, homosexuals, Jews, and all the people who come from different ethnicities. Actually, he defines himself as "a dirty little dosser". (258) Among the people, his hatred is targeted towards the black most. He becomes a typical Nazi and patrols the streets with his friends in his "leather jacket" (331). His sister, who loves him more than anybody among the family members, complains that he has become "worse than dad" (84). Since the novel's central theme is racism and xenophobia, the author bases it on a real-life murder of a black teenager and similarly, Dirk achieves his goal by killing Winston, a black man, mercilessly. "This tragic event displays the extent of prejudice, xenophobia and hatred towards to the black" people in England (Düzgün, 46).

Conclusion

All in all, in the novel Maggie Gee displays the conditions of non-white people in England who are regarded as inferiors, and who are faced with difficulties stem from their ethnicities. Due to the fact that they hold remarkable positions in the country, and because of the probability of losing superiority over foreigners, Englishmen regard them as a sort of menace which eventually causes fear and hatred. The author's one of the main premise is to convey the issue of British identity, and British people's attitudes to those who do not carry pure English blood. Their sense of superiority leads to xenophobia, racial hatred, and even violence.

Foreigners, no matter how kind they are or compatible with the society, are not welcomed but still regarded as 'the other' by racist English people. Even in public places such as parks, hospitals, schools, or churches, they cannot tolerate seeing foreigners. In multicultural countries like England, xenophobia causes a rejection of the lifestyles, and cultural or religious values of immigrants for fear of being invaded or surpassed both sociologically and economically. The author's, as an English woman, depiction of her own country's people as racists is a crucial phenomenon that signifies a global problem faced by immigrants. It also unrolls a reality that fear or discomfort, which are derived from non-native people's

compulsory act of leaving their countries and settling into a new place is a global problem experienced nowadays, which also increases day by day.

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